

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives.

Part III.* Synthesis of Furoquinolines

R. J. CHUDGAR & K. N. TRIVEDI

Department of Chemistry, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-2

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2-Methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol on ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation gave 2-methyl-3-acetaldehyde-4-quinolinol, which on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid gave 4-methylfure (3, 3-c) quinoline (IIIa). Similarly 2,8-dimethyl- and 6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol on ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation and ring closure with polyphosphoric acid gave 4,6-dimethylfure (3,2-c) quinoline (IIIb) and 8-methoxy-4-methylfure (3,2-c) quinoline (IIIc) respectively. Several substituted α -allylacetoacetarylamides have been cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to give 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethylfure (2,3-b) quinoline derivatives; these α -allyl derivatives on hydrogenation with palladised charcoal afforded α -propyl acetoacetarylamides which underwent cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid to give 4-methyl-3-propylcarbostyryl derivatives.

In continuation of our previous work¹ on the synthesis of quinoline derivatives, we report here the synthesis of furo (3,2-c) quinoline derivatives. *o*-Hydroxyallylquinolines, obtained by the Claisen rearrangement of 4-allyloxyquinoline derivatives were subjected to ozonolysis² followed by ring closure to furoquinolines by polyphosphoric acid,

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2-Methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol³ (Ia) when subjected to ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation in the presence of palladised charcoal afforded 2-methyl-3-acetaldehyde-4-quinolinol (IIa) which on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid gave 4-methylfuro(3,2-c)quinoline (IIIa). This was found to be identical by mixed m.p. determination with the compound prepared earlier⁴ by condensation of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-quinolinol with ethylbromomalonate followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation.

2,8-Dimethyl-4-quinolinol on allylation with allylbromide in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave 2,8-dimethyl-4-allyloxyquinoline which on Claisen rearrangement afforded 2,8-dimethyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol (Ib). This on ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation gave 2,8-dimethyl-3-acetaldehyde-4-quinolinol (IIb) which on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid gave 4,6-dimethylfuro(3,2-c)quinoline (IIIb), identical with the one prepared earlier. Similarly 6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol on ozonolysis gave the corresponding 3-acetaldehyde derivative (IIc) which cyclised with PPA to 8-methoxy-4-methylfuro(3,2-c)quinoline identical with the one prepared earlier.

As α -allylacetoacetanilide (IV) on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-furo(2,3-b)quinoline (VII) and not 4-methyl-3-allyl-carbostyryl, an attempt was then made to prepare furo (2,3-b) quinoline derivatives having no substituent in the furan ring by subjecting this α -allyl derivative to ozonolysis followed by ring closure with conc sulphuric acid. When α -allylacetoacetanilide (IV) was subjected to ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation, it did not give the corresponding acetaldehyde derivative but instead α -propylacetoacetanilide (V) was isolated. The same α -propyl derivative (V) was obtained when α -allyl-acetoacetanilide was subjected to hydrogenation in the presence of palladised charcoal. This on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid gave 4-methyl-3-propylcarbostyryl (VI).

In a very similar manner 4,8-dimethyl-3-propyl-carbostyryl and 6-methoxy-4-methyl-3-propylcarbostyryl were prepared from acetoacet-*o*-toluidide and acetoacet-*p*-anisidide respectively by allylation, hydrogenation followed by cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid.

Preparation of several 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-furo(2,3-b)quinoline derivatives having substituents like methyl, methoxy and chloro in the benzenoid part of the quinoline ring was carried out by cyclising the α -allyl-acetoacetarylamide derivatives.

2,8-Dimethyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol (Ib) on treatment with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2,3-dihydro-2,4,6-trimethyl-furo(3,2-c) quinoline (VIII). 2-Methyl-4-hydroxybenzo(*h*)quinoline on allylation gave 4-allyloxy derivative (IX) which on Claisen rearrangement gave 2-methyl-3-allyl-4-hydroxybenzo(*h*)quinoline (X). This (X) on treatment with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethylfuro(3,2-c)benzo(*h*)quinoline (XI). An attempt to dehydrogenate these dihydrofuroquinolines by palladised charcoal met with failure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ozonolysis of 2-methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol : 2-Methyl-3-acetaldehydo-4-quinolinol (IIa) : 2-Methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol (1 g.) was dissolved in formic acid (30 ml.) and the solution was cooled to about 15°. Ozone was passed through this solution for 1 hr. It was then hydrogenated at room temperature with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.; 5%) with continuous stirring in the atmosphere of hydrogen for 1½ hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The product which separated crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 230°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 71.20; H, 5.51; N, 6.58. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N requires C, 71.64; H, 5.47; N, 6.96%).

4-Methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IIIa) : The above acetaldehydo derivative (0.5 g.) was treated with polyphosphoric acid (8 g.) and heated on a water bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The product which separated crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 89°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 78.87; H, 4.81; N, 7.41. C₁₂H₉ON requires C, 78.68; H, 4.91; N, 4.64%).

2,8-Dimethyl-4-allyloxyquinoline : 2,8-Dimethyl-4-quinolinol (3.4 g.) was dissolved in ethyl methyl ketone (200 ml.) and refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (7 g.) and allylbromide (2.4 g.) on a water bath for 6 hr. The ethyl methyl ketone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The product which separated crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 61°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 78.70; H, 6.67; N, 6.55. C₁₄H₁₅ON requires C, 78.87; H, 7.04; N, 6.57%).

2,8-Dimethyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol (Ib) : The above allyloxy derivative (1 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 200–10° for 30 minutes. The product after washing with benzene crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 254°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 78.56; H, 6.88; N, 6.52. C₁₄H₁₅ON requires C, 78.87; H, 7.04; N, 6.57%).

2,8-Dimethyl-3-acetaldehydo-4-quinolinol (IIb) : The above allyl derivative (1 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (200 ml.) and the solution was cooled to 15°. Ozone was passed through this solution for 1 hr. It was then hydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.; 5%) with continuous stirring in the atmosphere of hydrogen for 1½ hr. After filtration the solution was concentrated to a small volume by distillation and mixed with ether

petroleum. The product which separated crystallised from xylene, m.p. 233°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 72.59; H, 6.33; N, 6.44. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 72.56; H, 6.04; N, 6.51%).

4,6-Dimethylfuro(3,2-c)quinoline (IIIb) : The above acetaldehyde derivative (0.5 g.) was heated on a water bath with polyphosphoric acid (8 g.) for 3 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 128°. Yield 0.15 g. (Found : C, 79.32; H, 5.76; N, 6.99. $C_{13}H_{11}ON$ requires C, 79.18; H, 5.58; N, 7.10%).

6-Methoxy-2-methyl-3-acetaldehyde-4-quinolinol (IIc) : 6-Methoxy-2-methyl-3-allyl-4-quinolinol (1 g.) was dissolved in formic acid (30 ml.) and the ozonolysis and hydrogenation were carried out as described above. The product crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 235°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 67.37; H, 5.56; N, 5.95. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 67.53; H, 5.62; N, 6.06%).

8-Methoxy-4-methyl-furo(3,2-c)quinoline (IIIc) : The above acetaldehyde derivative (0.5 g.) was heated on a water bath with polyphosphoric acid (8 g.) for 3 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 81°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 73.07; H, 4.88; N, 6.43. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 73.23; H, 5.16; N, 6.57%).

α -Allylacetoacetarylarnides : Sodium salt of acetoacetarylarnide was prepared by refluxing equimolecular quantities of pulverised sodium and acetoacetarylarnide in dry benzene for 6 hr. and then was treated with equimolecular quantity of allylbromide. The reaction mixture was refluxed further for 6-8 hr. It was poured over water and benzene layer separated and dried with anhydrous calcium chloride. On removing solvent the product obtained (Table I) was crystallised either from ether petroleum or benzene. Yield 55-60%.

TABLE I

 α -Allylacetoacetarylarnides

S.No.	α -Allyl acetoacet.	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis %					
				Required			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	<i>p</i> -anisidide	99	$C_{14}H_{17}O_3N$	68.01	6.88	5.66	67.92	6.55	5.70
2.	α -Naphthylarnide	117	$C_{17}H_{17}O_2N$	76.40	6.36	5.24	76.03	6.71	5.21
3.	<i>p</i> -Xylidide	128	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2N$	73.46	7.75	5.71	73.18	7.54	5.75
4.	<i>p</i> -chloroanilide	95	$C_{13}H_{14}O_2NCl$	62.01	5.56	5.56	61.90	5.41	5.69
5.	<i>o</i> -toluidide	90	$C_{14}H_{17}O_2N$	72.73	7.35	6.06	72.63	7.27	6.47

2,3-Dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-furo(2,3-h)quinoline derivatives : The above α -allyl derivative (1 g.) was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid (2 ml.) by heating in a water bath for 2 hr. It was poured over ice water and the separated product (Table II) crystallised from ether petroleum or benzene. Yield 0.5 g.

TABLE II

2,3-Dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-furo(2,3-b)quinoline derivatives

S.No.	Substituent in 2,3-dihydro-2,4- dimethyl-furo (2,3-h)quinoline (VI)	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %					
				Required			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	6-methoxy	122	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	73.35	6.55	6.11	73.18	6.44	5.93
2.	benzo(h)	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON	81.91	6.02	5.62	81.65	6.16	5.18
3.	5,8-dimethyl	147	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ IN	79.30	7.48	6.16	79.27	7.21	5.75
4.	6-chloro	130	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ONCl	66.80	5.13	5.99	66.68	4.78	5.66
5.	8-methyl	107	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ON	78.87	7.04	6.57	78.70	7.53	6.10

4-Methyl-3-propylcarbostyril (VI) : α -Allyl acetoacetanilide (0.5 g.) in ethyl acetate (20 ml.) was hydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.; 5%) with continuous stirring in the atmosphere of hydrogen for 1½ hr. The clear filtrate on evaporation gave the α -propyl acetoacetanilide (V) as thick oil. This was then treated with conc. sulphuric acid (2 ml.) and heated on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was added to water and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The product which separated crystallised from benzene, m.p. 175°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 77.87; H, 7.20; N, 7.20. C₁₃H₁₅ON requires C, 77.60; H, 7.46; N, 6.96%).

α -Propylacetoacet-o-toluidide : α -Allylacetoacet-o-toluidide (0.5 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (20 ml.) and was hydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.; 5%) as described above. Removal of the solvent after filtration gave the product which crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 97°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found : C, 71.91; H, 8.14; N, 5.71. C₁₄H₁₅O₂N requires C, 72.05; H, 8.15; N, 6.00%).

4,8-Dimethyl-3-propylcarbostyril : The above α -propyl derivative (0.5 g.) was heated on a water bath with conc. sulphuric acid (2 ml.) for 2 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 187°. Yield 0.15 g. (Found : C, 78.02; H, 7.70; N, 6.16. C₁₄H₁₇ON requires C, 78.13; H, 7.90; N, 6.51%).

α -Propylacetoacet-p-anisidide : α -Allylacetoacet-p-anisidide (0.5 g.) was dissolved in ethylacetate (20 ml.) and was hydrogenated with palladised charcoal (0.5 g.); 5% as described before. On working up as usual the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 80°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found : C, 67.67; H, 7.39; N, 5.98. C₁₄H₁₉O₃N requires C, 67.46; H, 7.67; N, 5.62%).

6-Methoxy-4-methyl-3-propylcarbostyril : The above α -propyl derivative (0.5 g.) was heated with conc. sulphuric acid (1 ml.) on a water bath for 1 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 195°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 72.53; H, 7.19; N, 5.80. C₁₄H₁₇O₂N requires C, 72.73; H, 7.35; N, 6.06%).

2-Methyl-4-allyloxy-benzo(h)quinoline (IX) : A mixture of 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-benzo(h)quinoline (3 g.), potassium carbonate (6 g.) and allylbromide (1.8 g.) was refluxed in dry

ethyl methyl ketone (150 ml.) for 7–8 hr. on a water bath. Solvent was evaporated after filtration and the separated product was purified by passing over alumina in benzene and finally crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 80°. Yield 1.2 g. (Found : C, 81.47; H, 6.41; N, 5.45. $C_{17}H_{15}ON$ requires C, 81.91; H, 6.02; N, 5.62%).

2-Methyl-3-allyl-4-hydroxy-benzo(h)quinoline (X) : The above allyloxy derivative (1 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 210–20° for 30 min. The product after washing with benzene was crystallised from dilute acetic acid (charcoal), m.p. 289–90°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 81.66; H, 6.26; N, 5.12. $C_{17}H_{15}ON$ requires C, 81.91; H, 6.02; N, 5.62%).

2,3-Dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-furo(3,2-c)benzo(h)quinoline (XI) : The above 3-allyl derivative (0.5 g.) was heated on a water bath with conc. sulphuric acid (1 ml. for 1 hr.). On working up as usual the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 128–30°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 81.43; H, 5.63; N, 5.18. $C_{17}H_{15}ON$ requires C, 81.91; H, 6.02; N, 5.62%).

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